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**PRIORITISING CONSERVATION ACTIONS TOWARDS THE SUSTAINABILITY OF THE DEHESA BY
INTEGRATING THE DEMANDS OF SOCIETY**

Carlos Parra-López^{1*}, Samir Sayadi¹, Guillermo Garcia-Garcia¹, Saker Ben Abdallah², Carmen
Carmona-Torres¹

¹Department of Agrifood System Economics. Institute of Agricultural and Fisheries Research and
Training (IFAPA). "Camino de Purchil" Centre. Camino de Purchil. PO Box 2027 - 18080 Granada,
Spain

²Department of Agricultural Engineering. Polytechnic University of Cartagena. P.º Alfonso XIII, 48. PO
Box 30203 Cartagena, Murcia, Spain

** Corresponding author: Tel: +34 671532146; e-mail: carlos.parra@juntadeandalucia.es (C. Parra-López)*

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1 Introduction

The dehesa is an important extensive agrosilvopastoral system in the Iberian Peninsula. The term dehesa is used only in Spain, but similar systems exist in other parts of the world, such as Portugal, North Africa and California (Consejería de Medio Ambiente, 2006). The value of this system lies in the products and services provided by its main components: trees, livestock and pasture. On dehesa farms, the most common trees are oaks (of the genus *Quercus*); livestock includes cattle, sheep and Iberian pigs; and some agricultural crops and shrubs can be found within the pastures (San Miguel, 1994; Horrillo et al., 2019). Dehesa farms cover an area of approximately 3.5 million ha in Spain and 1 million ha in Portugal, mainly in the southwest of the Iberian Peninsula (Bugalho et al., 2018). In addition to their direct economic value through primary production, mainly linked to food (e.g. ham, meat, sausages, cheese, asparagus, acorns, honey and mushrooms) and forest products (e.g. cork, wood, stoppers, charcoal), dehesa farms generate a diversity of jobs and processing and marketing industries. Recent research has shown that consumers' willingness to pay may be higher when the food purchased is advertised as being produced in the dehesa (Villanueva et al., 2021). In addition, the dehesa plays an important environmental and social role, as it offers a multitude of externalities (non-market functions). Environmental externalities include the maintenance of biodiversity, CO₂ fixation, soil protection, support for nutrient and water cycles, protection against erosion and desertification, and fire prevention. The social externalities of dehesa include the maintenance of population in rural areas, cultural heritage, aesthetic and recreational enjoyment, and the preservation of tradition and local knowledge (Olea and San Miguel-Ayanz, 2006; Campos et al., 2007; Gaspar et al., 2016).

In Andalusia, a region in southern Spain, the dehesa is an agroforestry system adapted to the constraints of the Mediterranean climate (i.e. hot, dry summers and mild winters) that has survived for centuries thanks to the balanced combination of productive factors and natural resources (Velasco Muñoz and Aznar Sánchez, 2016). The dehesa is distributed throughout the Andalusian region, especially in the less fertile areas dedicated to productive crops. It occupies an area of 1.2 million ha, approximately 14% of Andalusia, mainly in the provinces of Cordoba, Seville and Huelva, with holm oak being the most common tree (Consejería de Medio Ambiente, 2006). The average size of dehesa farms is 156.6 ha (Junta de Andalucía, 2009). The most important use of dehesa farms in Andalusia is grazing, followed by hunting, forestry and agriculture. Cattle, sheep, pigs and goats are the most common livestock in Andalusian dehesa (LIFE+ bioDehesa, 2016). At present, these ecosystems are

vulnerable due to their low economic profitability (WWF/Adena, 2014). In addition, other issues, such as environmental (e.g. drought, low plant regeneration, loss of trees, use of phytosanitary products) and social (e.g. ageing population, lack of farmers), aggravate the vulnerability of the dehesa. Costa Pérez et al. (2006) stated that Andalusian dehesa farms are at risk due to their intensity of exploitation and the lack of conservation and renewal of trees. These authors estimated that approximately 70% of Andalusian dehesa farms are damaged by biotic or abiotic agents, the most relevant of which are insects and mites, fungi and bacteria and, finally, human activities, mostly due to poor silvicultural practices. In addition, drought causes a shortage of pasture, a problem that is aggravated by the increased stocking of livestock in the dehesa during the summer (de Lázaro and Torres and González, 2012). This highlights the need to design and implement sustainable water storage practices.

The economic, environmental and social goods and services that are jointly produced by dehesa farms justify their multifunctional character, which contributes directly or indirectly to the well-being of society (Acosta et al., 2012; Acosta-Naranjo et al., 2020; Gomez-Giraldez et al., 2019; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003; Torralba et al., 2018; Velasco Muñoz and Aznar Sánchez, 2016). It is therefore necessary to design public policies to protect and support the dehesa, among other measures. Along these lines, the Common Agricultural Policy, starting with Agenda 2000 and its successive modifications, supports agricultural and livestock systems not only for their productive function, but also for their function as providers of other goods and services to society, which highlights their multifunctional role (Arriaza and Gómez-Limón, 2011; Campos et al., 2017; Carmona-Torres et al., 2014; Gómez-Limón et al., 2012; Groot et al., 2009; Kallas et al., 2007; Parra-López and Calatrava-Requena, 2006; Parra-López et al., 2008a; Rossing et al., 2007; Varela et al., 2020). Other EU policies and funds that aim to contribute to the provision of these goods and services are LIFE, the Structural Funds and cohesion actions. At the regional level in Andalusia, the Law of the Dehesa [Ley de la Dehesa] (Junta de Andalucía, 2010) and the Master Plan of Dehesa [Plan Director de la Dehesa] (CAPDER, 2017) support the economic and environmental viability of dehesa farms. However, studies assessing the contribution of the dehesa to the three dimensions of sustainability (environmental, economic and social) are still lacking. Furthermore, there is a need to propose actions to improve the sustainability of dehesa farms. The LIFE+ bioDehesa project (LIFE11 BIO/ES/000726) (<https://www.biodehesa.es>), in which this research is framed, aims to promote the sustainable and integrated management of dehesa farms in Andalusia through the dissemination of appropriate conservation actions and sub-actions, i.e. agroforestry and pastoral practices that address the main challenges related to their conservation.

In this context, the main objective of this work is to evaluate and prioritise different conservation actions/sub-actions (CAs/CSs) in the Andalusian dehesa according to their contribution to the improvement of its sustainability and, therefore, of the welfare of society as a whole. To this

end, a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) model based on the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) is developed and applied. The cornerstone of the evaluation is the integration of society's demands on the dehesa into the process, since sustainability is understood here to be associated with the general well-being of society. Thus, the priorities of the different CAs/CSs will be assessed in terms of their contribution to the satisfaction of a number of economic, environmental and social functions of the dehesa, which in turn are connected to different demands of society. The results are expected to contribute to the design of public policies towards greater sustainability of the dehesa. Furthermore, the methodological process presented here can serve as a guide to assess the sustainability associated with other management actions in other agro-ecological systems and/or in other regions.

2 Methodology

Figure 1 shows the methodological framework of this research, indicating the phases followed, the analyses and results obtained and the data sources used. All these issues are detailed in the following sections.

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Figure 1. Methodological framework

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2.1 Modelling with the Analytic Hierarchy Process

AHP is a discrete MCDA technique (Saaty, 1980; 2000) that allows the resolution of complex decision problems with multiple criteria and agents involved in scenarios of high uncertainty and risk. AHP is used here to define and evaluate a model of the relationships between CAs/CSs, their economic, environmental and social functions, and the relationships between these functions and society's demands on the dehesa, as described in the following sections.

2.1.1 Definition of the structure of the model

An AHP model is defined as a hierarchy of decision elements (i.e. the goal or overall objective at the top level of the hierarchy, and objectives and sub-objectives etc. at lower levels); these elements are interconnected by dominance (top-down)/contribution (bottom-up) relationships (Saaty, 1980). First, the goal, i.e. the overall objective, has to be set. In this case, the goal is to determine the CAs/CSs that most improve the sustainability of the Andalusian dehesa. The global priority of the different alternatives (CAs/CSs) measures the contribution of each of them to the satisfaction or achievement of the goal, i.e. the sustainability of the dehesa. However, the satisfaction of the goal requires the fulfilment of a number of objectives (demands of society on the dehesa) and sub-objectives (functions of the dehesa) by the CAs/CSs. The calculation of global priorities is shown below.

The definition of the structure of the AHP model for dehesa has involved three phases:

- 1) Defining the most relevant elements of the model, i.e. society's demands on the dehesa, the functions of the dehesa and the CAs/CSs.
 - a. In order to define society's demands on the dehesa, an extensive bibliographical review was carried out on the social demands on agriculture in general and the dehesa in particular. This bibliographical review made it possible to identify society's demands for agriculture and for the dehesa in particular, which were subsequently used in the questionnaire for the survey of society in the dehesa areas of Andalusia to be assessed (see next section). In addition, three focus group discussions were carried out with citizens of different profiles and close to the research team (10 people on 3 different days), who gave their opinion on the demands previously detected in the literature.
 - b. For the definition of the economic, environmental and social functions, secondary information on the multifunctionality of the dehesa was used, based on the three dimensions of sustainability (Sayadi and Parra-López, 2009). The choice of

functions was based on this literature review and the experience of the research team.

- c. Regarding CAs/CSs, in the context of the aforementioned LIFE+ bioDehesa project, a Network of Demonstration Dehesa Farms (NDDF) was created in rural areas with a presence of dehesa (Figure 2), in which 43 dehesa farms participate. The selection and characterisation of these farms can be found in Gómez Sal et al. (2016). This NDDF proposed a series of CAs/CSs to be tested to improve the sustainability of the dehesa.
- 2) Grouping the elements and establishing possible relationships between the elements of the model a priori without quantifying them. It is assumed that the different CAs/CSs would contribute to the different economic, environmental and social functions of the dehesa, and these functions would contribute to the satisfaction of society's demands.
- 3) Pre-testing and refinement of the proposed structure based on an evaluation by the research team and other project partners. As decision-makers continuously learn in the decision-making process, the AHP allows for feedback of subsequent information in the earlier stages of the process. In this study, the knowledge of the research team and other project partners was used to refine the structure of the AHP model for dehesa.

Figure 2. Areas of dehesa and NDDF in Andalusia

Source: LIFE+ bioDehesa Project (<https://www.uco.es/investigacion/proyectos/biodehesa/mapa-rdd>)

The final structure of the AHP model is shown in Figure 3. It consists of six levels of elements from top to bottom.

- 1) Goal (G): The objective is to determine the CAs/CSs that most improve the sustainability of the Andalusian dehesa.
- 2) Demands for sustainability (DS): This refers to society's demands on the dehesa in the three dimensions of sustainability: economic, environmental and social.
- 3) Economic, environmental and social demands (DEC, DEN and DSO): In addition, specific demands of society are classified within each of the three dimensions of sustainability specified in level 2. These are nine economic demands (DEC.1-DEC.9), six environmental demands (DEN.1-DEN.6) and six social demands (DSO.1-DSO.6). They are listed in the first row of Tables A.1-A.3 of Annex A.
- 4) Economic, environmental and social functions (FEC, FEN and FSO): Each group of demands can be satisfied by a group of dehesa functions in the same sustainability dimension. Eight economic functions (FEC.1-FEC.8) contributing to the satisfaction of economic demands, nine environmental functions (FEN.1-FEN.9) to environmental demands and five social functions (FSO.1-FSO.5) to social demands were defined. These are listed in the first column of Tables A.1-A.3 in Annex A.
- 5) Conservation actions (CA): Eight CAs (CA.1-CA.8) were defined to improve the sustainability of Andalusian dehesa farms. They are listed in the first column of Tables B.1-B.3 of Annex B.
- 6) Conservation sub-actions (CS): Each CA is subdivided into different CSs. Thirty-five CSs were proposed (CS.1.1-CS.8.5). They are listed in the first column of Table C in Annex C.

Figure 3. Structure of the AHP model for dehesa

2.1.2 Assessment of the relationships

Once the structure of the model has been defined, the relationships between the various elements need to be assessed. These relationships can be formally defined by means of a series of matrices. The matrices of the proposed model are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Relationship matrices of the AHP model (local priorities)

	G: Goal	DS: Demands for sustainability	DEC: Economic demands	DEN: Environmental demands	DSO: Social demands	FEC: Economic functions	FEN: Environmental functions	FSO: Social functions	CA: Conservation actions	CS: Conservation sub-actions
G: Goal										
DS: Demands for sustainability	$W_{DS,G}$									
DEC: Economic demands		$W_{DEC,DS}$								
DEN: Environmental demands		$W_{DEN,DS}$								
DSO: Social demands		$W_{DSO,DS}$								
FEC: Economic functions			$W_{FEC,DEC}$							
FEN: Environmental functions				$W_{FEN,DEN}$						
FSO: Social functions					$W_{FSO,DSO}$					
CA: Conservation actions						$W_{CA,FEC}$	$W_{CA,FEN}$	$W_{CA,FSO}$		
CS: Conservation sub-actions									$W_{CS,CA}$	

Each row of the matrix represents the local priorities of each child element with respect to its parent element, i.e. how the different child elements contribute to satisfy the parent element on which they depend. For example, each row of the matrix $W_{CS,CA}$, indicates how the different CSs contribute to each CA, i.e. what are the local priorities of each CS within each CA.

AHP allows these priorities to be assessed using different types of data (hard and soft), methods (pairwise and direct) and scales (ratio, graphical, verbal) (Forman and Selly, 2001). In fact, AHP allows for the incorporation of quantitative and hard data information, if available, and qualitative, subjective and intangible information, for example in the form of expert knowledge and/or stakeholder preferences, into the assessment process, which is one of its strengths (Parra-López et al., 2021). When the number of items to be compared is large, as in this study, direct elicitation (Bottomley and Doyle, 2001; Larichev et al., 1995) may be the most operational and practical method (Carmona-Torres et al., 2014). In particular, a "direct rating" weighting method was used, as proposed by Parra-

López et al. (2008b), using a rating scale, ranging from 1 (very weak contribution) to 9 (very strong contribution), where scale point 9 is 9/1 times greater than scale point 1, 9/2 times greater than 2, and so on.

Two primary sources of information were used to assess the relationships within the model.

- 1) Survey of society in the dehesa areas of Andalusia (questionnaire in Annex F): This survey was carried out among Andalusian citizens in the regions where dehesa farms are present in order to assess the economic, environmental and social demands on the dehesa. In other words, it was used to assess the relationships between the elements of levels 1 to 3 (Figure 3). The questionnaire consisted of these groups of items: i) Level of knowledge and general opinions; ii) Social preferences in relation to the functions and externalities of the dehesa; and iii) Basic data of the interviewee. Once the structured questionnaire was designed, a pre-test was carried out with 30 participants to assess their understanding. This pre-test was not included in the final analysis. Subsequently, the sampling was stratified with a proportional allocation according to 1) population at municipal level: three categories of municipalities were defined according to population size and a correction according to population density (rural, urban and metropolitan); and 2) the relative importance of the dehesa area according to the percentage of dehesa in the total area of the municipality (category 1 - 0%, category 2 - between 0% and 30%, and category 3 - more than 30%). Combining both categories, eight different types of municipalities were obtained, as no metropolitan municipality was found with a percentage of dehesa surface area greater than 30%. In order to obtain statistical representativeness within each stratum, the percentage representation by sex (men: 50%; women: 50%) and age (18-34: 34.6%; 35-49: 28.4%; 50-64: 18.8%; 65 and over: 18.2%) has been respected. Finally, 308 face-to-face interviews were conducted during the second quarter of 2017 with citizens resident in Andalusia, resulting in a sampling error of 5.66% for intermediate proportions ($p=q=0.5$) and dichotomous variables, assuming a 95% confidence interval.
- 2) Interviews with dehesa experts (questionnaire in Annex G): The objective was to assess the relationships between the elements of levels 3 to 6 (Figure 3). The questionnaire consisted of different blocks of questions: 1) Interviewee data; 2) Effects of sub-actions on conservation actions; 3) Effects of conservation actions on functions; and 4) Effects of functions on the demands of society. Expert knowledge was used because of the complex nature of the issues investigated (relationships between demands, functions, conservation actions and sub-actions) for which reliable (hard) data are not generally available. The

validity of expert knowledge is due to the fact that it is based on information that is supported and corroborated by observed or measured assessments in other studies and that can be synthesised by the expert for the ad hoc assessment in question. The experts were selected because of their close relationship with and knowledge of the dehesa. Thus, in the last quarter of 2017 and the first quarter of 2018, 16 experts were interviewed, 5 of them from the Public Administration (Agricultural and Fisheries Management Agency of Andalusia, AGAPA), 4 from Public Research Bodies (Institute of Agricultural and Fisheries Research and Training - IFAPA), 4 from the University (three from the University of Cordoba and one field technician), 2 were technicians from agricultural organisations, and 1 owner/manager of a dehesa farm.

2.1.3 Aggregation of priorities

Once the individual matrices were obtained for each of the citizens and experts interviewed, they were integrated into their corresponding aggregated matrices using the Aggregation of Individual Priorities (AIP) method (Ramanathan and Ganesh, 1994). With this method, each element of the aggregated matrix is obtained as the arithmetic mean of the individual priorities of all individuals in the group. Many experts were not aware of all the relationships in the matrix, and their knowledge may have focused on some sub-matrices. Our aim was to have at least some responses for all elements of the relationship matrices. The aggregated responses include all expert responses and can be considered more reliable than those of individual expert groups (Public Administration, Public Research Bodies, etc.).

The aggregated matrices of the experts' assessments are given in Annexes A-C. These Annexes show the normalised contribution of each function/CA/CS to each demand/function/CA. For example, Table A.1 in Annex A shows that the function *FEC.1. Agricultural production (crops)* contributes with a value of 0.1130 to the demand *DEC.1. Typical, safe, healthy and quality agricultural products*. Finally, the aggregate demands of society are presented in the Results section.

2.1.4 Synthesis of priorities

Once the local priorities of all the elements of the model were aggregated, they were synthesised. That is, the priorities of the lower level elements of the hierarchy (in this study, demands, functions and CAs/CSs) were transferred to the goal (or any intermediate element of the AHP model), to obtain their global (or final) priorities. This was done by a weighted sum of the local priorities of the

lower-level elements by the local priorities of the intermediate-level elements (Ben-Abdallah et al., 2018). This weighted sum is equivalent to a multiplication of the local priorities relationship matrices (Table 1). The multiplications used in this study are as follows:

- Demands of society on the dehesa (global priorities):

$$\mathbf{W}_{D,G} = (\mathbf{W}_{Di,DS}) * \mathbf{W}_{DS,G}, \text{ with } i=EC,EN,SO$$

- Functions of the dehesa according to the demands of society (global priorities):

$$\mathbf{W}_{F,G} = (\mathbf{W}_{Fi,Dj}) * \mathbf{W}_{D,G}, \text{ with } i=j=EC,EN,SO$$

- Functions of the dehesa according to the demands of society (final priorities for each dimension of sustainability):

$$\mathbf{W}_{F,DS} = (\mathbf{W}_{Fi,Dj}) * (\mathbf{W}_{Di,DS}), \text{ with } i=j=EC,EN,SO$$

- Conservation actions according to the demands of society (global priorities):

$$\mathbf{W}_{CA,G} = (\mathbf{W}_{CA,Fj}) * \mathbf{W}_{F,G}, \text{ with } j=EC,EN,SO$$

- Conservation sub-actions according to the demands of society (global priorities):

$$\mathbf{W}_{CS,G} = \mathbf{W}_{CS,CA} * \mathbf{W}_{CA,G}$$

Matrices in parentheses are composed of different matrices summed by rows or columns, as appropriate in each case. For example:

$$(\mathbf{W}_{Di,DS}) \text{ (with } i = EC, EN, SO) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{W}_{DEC,DS} \\ \mathbf{W}_{DEN,DS} \\ \mathbf{W}_{DSO,DS} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$(\mathbf{W}_{Fi,Dj}) \text{ (with } i = j = EC, EN, SO) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{W}_{FEC,DEC} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{W}_{FEN,DEN} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{W}_{FSO,DSO} \end{pmatrix}$$

2.2 Identification of critical conservation sub-actions

Critical CSs are defined as CSs with 1) a high priority (according to the demands of society), and 2) a high margin for implementation, i.e. they are currently not widespread. The global priorities of CSs have already been defined ($\mathbf{W}_{CS,G}$). The margin for implementation (MI_i) of a CS_i is defined as the proportion of dehesa farms, from 0 to 1, that have not implemented that CS. In other words:

$$MI_i = 1 - DI_i$$

where DI_i is the degree of implementation of the CS_i . For example, for a CS_i implemented in 70% of the dehesa farms ($DI_i = 0.7$), $MI_i = 1 - 0.7 = 0.3$. A survey of Andalusian dehesa farms was carried out in the last quarter of 2017 and the first quarter of 2018 to determine the degree of implementation (DI) of each CS at present (questionnaire in Annex H). As indicated above, in the framework of the LIFE+

bioDehesa project, a Network of Demonstration Dehesa Farms (NDDF) was created in rural areas with a presence of dehesa, made up of 43 dehesa farms. 24 dehesa farms within the NDDF participated in this survey. In addition, 14 dehesa farms outside but close to the NDDF were selected and participated in the survey. The 38 (24+14) active owners/managers of the dehesa farms were interviewed face-to-face following this structured questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of these groups of questions: 1) Farm characteristics; 2) Sector needs; 3) Conservation actions and sub-actions (pre-project); 4) Farming dedication; 5) Attitudes and opinions towards innovation; and 6) Personal details of the respondent.

Finally, a criticality indicator CI_i is defined for each CS_i as follows:

$$CI_i = W_{CS_i,G} * MI_i$$

with $W_{CS_i,G}$ being the global priorities of the CS_i . The CI makes it possible to determine the CSs with the greatest potential to improve the sustainability of the Andalusian dehesa.

2.3 Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to assess how the ranking of the CAs would change when considering the demands of society in only one of the three dimensions of sustainability (economic, environmental and social demands), assuming that the importance of the other dimensions is equal to 0. The usefulness of this analysis is to determine how the priorities of the CAs change according to the importance assigned to each sustainability domain.

For this purpose, four scenarios were analysed and compared:

- 1) Base scenario (B-Sc): Ranking of CAs considering the global demands of society, i.e. integrating the three dimensions of sustainability (society's demands on dehesa - global priorities ($W_{D,G}$)).
- 2) Economic scenario (Eco-Sc): Ranking of CAs considering only the economic demands of society (society's economic demands on dehesa - local priorities ($W_{DEC,DS}$)).
- 3) Environmental scenario (Env-Sc): Ranking of CAs considering only the environmental demands of society (society's environmental demands on dehesa - local priorities ($W_{DEN,DS}$)).
- 4) Social scenario (Soc-Sc): Ranking of CAs taking into account only the social demands of society (society's social demands on dehesa - local priorities ($W_{DSO,DS}$)).

3 Results

3.1 Demands of the society on the dehesa

The demands of Andalusian society related to the environmental dimension of dehesa sustainability show the highest priority (0.3712), with a significant difference over the other dimensions, economic (0.3195) and social (0.3093), which have similar priorities (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Society's demands for the sustainability dimensions of dehesa (local priorities) ($W_{DS,G}$)

The local priorities of society's demands on the dehesa within the three dimensions of sustainability are shown in Annex D. It should be noted that:

- Among the economic demands of Andalusian society on the dehesa, the most relevant are *DEC.1. Typical, safe, healthy and quality agricultural products* (0.1280) and *DEC.9. Leisure, recreation, rural tourism and eco-tourism* (0.1240). They are followed by *DEC.2. Beekeeping products* (0.1193) and *DEC.3. Forest products: cork, acorns, wood, etc.* (0.1179).
- The environmental demands of Andalusian society have very similar priorities. The priority of the demands *DEN.6. Typical and quality landscape production* (0.1713) and *DEN.1. Conservation and maintenance of species of wild flora and fauna and proliferation of wildlife (biodiversity)* (0.1696) are slightly higher than the rest. The demands *DEN.3. Regulation of water cycles, contribution to water balance, increase of quality of reservoir water and recharge of aquifers and soil capacity* (0.1626) and *DEN.2. Conservation of soils and reduction of erosive phenomena and landslides* (0.1629) are the lowest priority environmental demands.

- c) The highest priority social demands are *DSO.4 Historical and cultural heritage of the dehesa* (0.1798) and *DSO.3 Educational, cultural and scientific uses of dehesa land* (0.1792). *DSO.1 Contribution to social cohesion* (0.1463) is the least important social demand.

The global priorities of the demands of Andalusian society on the dehesa (Figure 5) were calculated by weighting the local priorities of the demands within each dimension of sustainability (Annex D) by the global priority of each dimension (Figure 4). The highest priority demands are *DEN.6. Typical and quality landscape production* (0.0636) and *DEN.1. Conservation and maintenance of species of wild flora and fauna, and proliferation of wildlife (biodiversity)* (0.0630), followed by the rest of the environmental demands. They are followed by social demands, the most important being *DSO.4 Historical and cultural heritage of the dehesa* (0.0556) and *DSO.3 Educational, cultural and scientific uses of dehesa land* (0.0554). Economic demands have a lower priority, the most important being *DEC.1. Typical, safe, healthy and quality agricultural products* (0.0409) and *DEC.9. Leisure, recreation, rural tourism and eco-tourism* (0.0396).

Figure 5. Society's demands on dehesa (global priorities) ($W_{D,G}$)

3.2 Priorities of the functions of the dehesa

This section presents the priorities of the different functions of the dehesa according to the demands of society, considering these demands (from the previous section), and the relationship between the functions of the dehesa and the demands of society based on expert knowledge (Annex A). The final priorities of these functions are shown in Annex E. It should be noted that:

- a) Within the economic functions, *FEC.3. Forest production (acorns, cork, wood, etc.)* stands out (0.1876), followed by *FEC.7. Gross profitability of the farm* (0.1455) and *FEC.5. Production of other products (honey, mushrooms, truffles, etc.)* (0.1407).
- b) The highest priority environmental function when considering society's environmental demands on the dehesa is *FEN.1. Biodiversity* (0.1600), followed by *FEN.2. Reduction of erosion* (0.1251) and *FEN.8. Prevention of forest fires* (0.1185).
- c) All social functions have a similar priority. The highest priority functions are *FSO.4. Preservation of the intangible cultural heritage* (0.2128), *FSO.3. Preservation of the tangible cultural heritage* (0.2061) and *FSO.1. Creation of direct and indirect local employment* (0.2051).

At the global level (Figure 6), the priorities of the social functions stand out, especially *FSO.4. Preservation of the intangible cultural heritage* (0.0658) and *FSO.3. Preservation of the tangible cultural heritage* (0.0637). *FEC.3. Forest production (acorn, cork, wood, etc.)* (0.0599), which is economic, and *FEN.1. Biodiversity* (0.0594), which is environmental, are also functions of the dehesa with a high priority according to society's demands.

Figure 6. Functions of dehesa according to society's demands (global priorities) ($W_{F,G}$)

3.3 Priorities of the conservation actions

Figure 7 shows the priorities of the different CAs according to the demands of society, taking into account the priorities of the functions of the dehesa (previous section) and the relationship between CAs and functions based on expert knowledge (Annex B). The CAs with the highest priority are CA.6. Soil and water conservation (0.1573) and CA.1. Renewal of trees (0.1506), followed by CA.4. Conservation, diversification and improvement of grasslands (0.1286).

Figure 7. Conservation actions according to society's demands (global priorities) ($W_{CA,G}$)

3.4 Priorities of the conservation sub-actions

This section shows the priorities of the different CSs (Figure 8) according to the demands of society, taking into account the CAs (from the previous section) and the relationship between CSs and CAs based on expert knowledge (Annex C). The CSs with the highest priority are *CS.2.1. Formation pruning* (0.0462) and *CS.2.3. Health pruning* (0.0429), both within *CA.2. Management of trees*. The following are CSs within *CA.7. Integrated control of tree pests and diseases* and *CA.6 Soil and water conservation* and, such as *CS.7.3. Limestone amendments* (0.0420) and *CS.6.4. Conservation of vegetation on riverbanks and watercourses* (0.0414).

Figure 8. Conservation sub-actions according to society's demands (global priorities) ($W_{cs,g}$)

3.5 Critical conservation sub-actions

The degree of implementation (DI) of the different CSs in the Andalusian dehesa farms interviewed is shown in Table 2. The least implanted CSs are *CS.4.6. Electric shepherd* (implemented by only 7.89% of the dehesa farms) and *CS.5.4. Creation and/or conservation of patches of shrub vegetation in low-productive areas* (implemented by 10.53%). These are, therefore, the CSs with the highest margin for implementation (MI = 0.921 and 0.895, respectively).

Table 2. Degree of implementation of conservation sub-actions in the Andalusian dehesa

Conservation sub-actions	DI
CS.1.1 Sowing acorns with installation of individual protectors	0.4737
CS.1.2 Planting with installation of individual protectors	0.4737
CS.1.3 Thinning of bushes to select the best specimens	0.3684
CS.1.4 Installation of individual protectors to protect existing natural regenerated plants	0.3421
CS.1.5 Temporary restriction of grazing in an area by means of a perimeter fence to favour the growth of natural regeneration	0.3684
CS.2.1. Formation pruning	0.6579
CS.2.2. Maintenance pruning	0.6842
CS.2.3. Health pruning	0.7368
CS.3.1. Adequacy of livestock feeders and/or drinkers to prevent access to wildlife and avoid shared use	0.3158
CS.3.2. Elements that facilitate the handling of animals such as salting places, or portable troughs and feeders	0.5000
CS.3.3. Enclosures with livestock and/or hunting nets that facilitate the handling of the animals	0.6316
CS.4.1. Triple NPK fertilization	0.2895
CS.4.2. Phosphoric fertilization	0.3947
CS.4.3. Calcium fertilization	0.1842
CS.4.4. Introduction of legumes (grassland) and fertilizers	0.4737
CS.4.5. Manuring	0.2368
CS.4.6. Electric shepherd	0.0789
CS.4.7 Temporary grassland reserves to ensure seed dispersal (reserve at any time of year)	0.4737
CS.4.8 Grazing management to improve pasture: fertilizing and seed dispersal	0.5789
CS.5.1. Reforestation of riverbanks and watercourses	0.2368
CS.5.2. Creation and/or conservation of hedges on borders, paths or next to stone walls	0.2368
CS.5.3. Diversification of tree feet	0.1579
CS.5.4. Creation and/or conservation of patches of shrub vegetation in low-productive areas	0.1053
CS.6.1. Correction of gullies by masonry	0.1842
CS.6.2. Scrub clearance by strips when there is a steep slope	0.2895
CS.6.3 Ploughing following contours	0.4474
CS.6.4 Conservation of vegetation on riverbanks and watercourses	0.3421
CS.7.1. Installation and use of sanitary fords	0.2368
CS.7.2. Installation of nests	0.3684

CS.7.3. Limestone amendments	0.2368
CS.8.1. Conservation of traditional stone walls	0.5526
CS.8.2. Implantation or conservation of bee or aromatic flora species	0.3158
CS.8.3. Adaptation or creation of troughs and/or ponds for wildlife and their maintenance	0.3158
CS.8.4 Creation and rehabilitation of structures that serve as refuges for fauna (adapted tiles, etc.)	0.2895
CS.8.5 Rehabilitation of traditional non-habitable rural infrastructure such as fountains, swimming pools, wells, pigeon houses, pigeon lofts, etc.	0.5263

Figure 9 shows the CSs according to their priorities and margins for implementation. The most critical CSs (in the upper right corner of the Figure), with the greatest potential to improve the sustainability of Andalusian dehesa due to their high criticality indicator (CI) are CS.6.1. *Correction of gullies by masonry* (CI = 0.335) and CS.7.3. *Limestone amendments* (0.0321). These are some of the CSs that owners/managers of dehesa farms should focus on to improve their sustainability, to say the most critical ones.

Figure 9. Criticality indicators for conservation sub-actions according to their margin for implementation and priority

3.6 Sensitivity of conservation actions

Table 3 shows the prioritisation and ranking of the CAs in the scenarios defined in the section 2.3. The highest priority CAs with respect to the overall demands of society are CA.6. *Soil and water conservation* (0.1573) and CA.1. *Renewal of trees* (0.1506) for the baseline scenario

(B-Sc), as set out in section 3.3. The priority of *CA.6. Soil and water conservation (0.1573)* and *CA.1. Renewal of trees* also score highest if only the economic demands of society (Eco-Sc) and the environmental demands of society (Env-Sc) are taken into account. However, these results vary slightly if only the social demands of society (Soc-Sc) are taken into account, where *CA.1. Renewal of trees* ranks first, followed by *CA.8. Diversification of habitats*. In all scenarios, *CA.3. Minimization of contacts between livestock and hunting fauna* is ranked last.

Therefore, the ranking of the CAs changes when considering different demands of society, i.e. it is sensitive to demands, although there are some CAs that stand out more in almost all scenarios. Thus, meeting societal demands would, in general, imply focusing on *CA.6. Soil and water conservation*. However, meeting only the social demands of society would imply a focus on *CA.1. Renewal of trees*. In any case, it should be noted that non-baseline scenarios are extreme situations, where only one type of societal demand (sustainability dimension) is taken into account. Normally, policy decisions seek a balance between the three dimensions of sustainability.

1

Table 3. Sensitivity analysis of conservation actions priorities and raking

Priority/ranking of CAs	CA.1. Renewal of trees		CA.2. Management of trees		CA.3. Minimization of contacts between livestock and hunting fauna		CA.4. Conservation, diversification and improvement of grasslands		CA.5. Diversification of tree and shrub vegetation associated with dehesas		CA.6. Soil and water conservation		CA.7. Integrated control of tree pests and diseases		CA.8. Diversification of habitats	
	Priority	Ranking	Priority	Ranking	Priority	Ranking	Priority	Ranking	Priority	Ranking	Priority	Ranking	Priority	Ranking	Priority	Ranking
B-Sc. CAs according to society's global demands (global priorities)	0.1506	2	0.1170	7	0.0856	8	0.1286	3	0.1200	5	0.1573	1	0.1210	4	0.1199	6
Eco-Sc. CAs according to society's economic demands (global priorities)	0.1523	2	0.1140	5	0.0853	8	0.1345	3	0.1048	7	0.1728	1	0.1312	4	0.1051	6
Env-Sc. CAs according to society's environmental demands (global priorities)	0.1507	2	0.1119	6	0.0715	8	0.1414	3	0.1292	4	0.1655	1	0.1105	7	0.1193	5
Soc-Sc. CAs according to society's social demands (global priorities)	0.1488	1	0.1262	4	0.1028	8	0.1071	7	0.1247	5	0.1314	3	0.1228	6	0.1361	2

2

4 Discussion

4.1 *Conceptual approach*

Multifunctionality of agriculture (and by extension of agroforestry) is a concept that refers to the multiple products, services and benefits that a single agricultural/agroforestry system or a single piece of land can produce (Van Huylenbroeck et al., 2007). From a theoretical perspective, multifunctionality has the potential to increase the sustainability and productivity of agricultural/agroforestry systems while providing a range of services and benefits to the environment, society and the economy. In practice, multifunctionality can provide numerous advantages, such as more efficient production, better use of resources and increased resilience. However, multifunctionality has some limitations. From a theoretical point of view, it can be difficult to balance different objectives, as some multifunctional activities may conflict with each other (Kato and Ahern, 2009). From a practical point of view, increased complexity may lead to higher costs and the need for more specialised skills and knowledge (Romstad et al., 2000). In addition, multifunctionality may lead to reduced production of some commodities and may not always be economically viable. Overall, multifunctionality can bring many benefits to agricultural/agroforestry systems, but there are also some potential conflicts that need to be taken into account. Careful planning and management are needed to ensure a balance of objectives. In the model proposed for dehesa in this study, AHP allowed for the joint consideration and assessment of a wide range of criteria and sub-criteria, such as demands of society and the functions of the dehesa, in the three dimensions of sustainability.

Furthermore, the sustainability approach used in this research focuses on the total economic, environmental and social costs and benefits of a particular agricultural/agroforestry system. It emphasises the need to balance economic, social and environmental costs and benefits to ensure long-term sustainability. However, it is not the only approach that exists. For example, the ecosystem services approach (e.g. de Groot and Braat, 2015) focuses on identifying, assessing and quantifying the services provided by agricultural ecosystems, such as soil fertility, water supply and pollination. This approach emphasises the importance of understanding the full range of services provided by agricultural systems to ensure their sustainable management. Alternatively, the complex social-ecological systems approach (e.g. Berkes et al., 2003) takes into account the interactions between human and natural systems.

This approach emphasises the importance of understanding the social, political and economic contexts in which farming systems are embedded, as well as the interactions between human and natural processes to ensure that farming systems are managed sustainably. All three approaches focus on the interactions between environment, society and economy and emphasise the importance of ecosystems, natural resources and human activities. The three approaches offer different ways of understanding and addressing human-environment interactions, and can be used together to inform sustainable development strategies and policies.

This study implicitly adopts the principle of weak sustainability, as opposed to the idea of strong sustainability (e.g. Neumayer, 2010). Both weak and strong sustainability are based on the principles of sustainable development, which is the idea of meeting present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Weak sustainability is based on the idea of replacing natural capital with other forms of capital, while strong sustainability emphasises the need to maintain and restore natural capital. Weak sustainability focuses more on economic growth, while strong sustainability focuses more on the long-term ecological health of the environment. Weak sustainability is more flexible and adaptive, while strong sustainability is more prescriptive and limits certain activities to ensure that future generations have the same resources. The principle of weak sustainability, adopted in this research, allows for the possibility of trade-offs between economic, social and environmental objectives. This approach recognises that economic growth can be beneficial to society, but also recognises the need to protect the environment. This principle also allows for the inclusion of social objectives in decision-making, such as equity, inclusion and access to basic services. However, the weak sustainability principle may be limited in its ability to address some of the more complex and systemic issues surrounding sustainability. For example, it does not address the root causes of environmental degradation and can be seen as a way to avoid more difficult conversations about the need for systemic change. Furthermore, the weak sustainability principle does not adequately take into account the long-term impacts of environmental degradation and may lead to decisions that are not necessarily in the best interests of the environment.

The principle of weak sustainability has implications for MCDA, the basis of the methodology used in this research. MCDA in general, and AHP in particular, are tools used to evaluate and compare different options for decision-making, taking into account multiple criteria such as economic, social and environmental objectives. The weak sustainability principle

can be used to inform the evaluation criteria used in MCDA, allowing trade-offs between objectives. In addition, the weak sustainability principle has implications for policy making, as it can help guide decision-making in a way that takes into account economic, environmental and social objectives. This approach can help to ensure that policies are developed taking into account the long-term sustainability of environmental and social issues.

4.2 Methodology and data

AHP, the methodology used here to assess the sustainability of the dehesa, makes the decision-making process more transparent by making the preferences of the different agents involved more explicit, which facilitates the detection of conflicting elements (Parra-López et al., 2008a). Furthermore, it allows for the quantification of qualitative information and continuous learning by decision-makers, so that the information obtained can be fed back into the initial stages of the decision-making process (Saaty, 2000; Forman and Selly, 2001). However, AHP also has methodological weaknesses and limitations that need to be taken into account when assessing the sustainability of agricultural/agroforestry systems. Firstly, AHP can be a subjective process if hard data is not available, as is common in sustainability assessments and in this study. In this case, AHP relies heavily on expert knowledge, which can lead to biases and errors in the assessment. Furthermore, it is difficult to quantify the relative importance of the different criteria, as the weights assigned to them are may have a certain degree of subjectivity and may be difficult to compare between different assessments. Furthermore, the AHP method is often based on pairwise comparison of criteria, which can lead to inconsistencies and errors in the assessment. This is because the relative importance of criteria may change depending on the order in which they are compared. Furthermore, it can be difficult to compare criteria between different stakeholders, as their preferences and opinions may differ. Finally, AHP is a static process, which means that it cannot take into account changes in the environment and other factors that may affect the sustainability of the farming/agroforestry system over time. This can lead to inaccurate assessments and an inability to respond to changes in the system.

Otherwise, AHP is a fully compensatory method aligned with weak sustainability (for a review of the relationship between AHP and the sustainability approach, see Munda (2008; 2016)). This means that AHP allows trade-offs between environmental, economic and social objectives and balances them to achieve a sustainable outcome. The proposed AHP model for

dehesa is based on the principle that all components of sustainability should be taken into account in decision-making, and that decisions should be made in a way that maximises the overall benefit to society. This approach is in line with the weak sustainability approach, which seeks to balance the needs of the environment, the economy and society. This approach allows decision-makers to assess the trade-offs between different objectives and identify the best option in terms of global sustainability.

In this context, it should be noted that the Analytic Network Process (ANP) methodology (Saaty, 2013), which is a generalisation of AHP, can be useful for a more accurate assessment of CAs/CSs. Indeed, ANP allows multiple criteria (such as economic, environmental and social) and interdependencies between them to be considered. AHP does not take these interdependencies into account, which can be seen as a limitation of the method.

As for the data obtained as primary information, it was collected in 2017 and 2018, as indicated in the Methodology section. It is not expected that the data from the expert interviews will change much in such a short time to the present day, as they basically refer to the relationships between demands of society and CAs/CSs which are technical issues. Similarly, the data obtained in the survey of the dehesa farms should not change much in a short period of time, as they refer to the CSs implemented by the owners/managers, which should not change too much in the short term. Finally, the data obtained in the survey of Andalusian society, which refer to their demands, may be more likely to become somewhat outdated more easily. However, we consider that these data are still valid as we do not believe that these demands have changed substantially in the short term, as they refer specifically to the dehesa and are somewhat general and timeless. Nevertheless, this should be taken into account when interpreting the results obtained in this work.

4.3 Results

Although the proposed framework and the AHP approach are not very novel in combining societal priorities with quantitative approaches to assess the effects of management on sustainability indicators (see e.g. Parra-López et al. 2009), its application to dehesa is new to our knowledge. In this section we discuss the results obtained and compare them with those of other related studies. It is important to note that each study has its own set of indicators and dimensions, as well as different objectives and scope; therefore, comparisons are not always

straightforward. For example, Franco et al. (2012) analysed extensive dehesa livestock systems using indicators related to adaptability, stability, self-management, productivity and equity, which, although they fit into the economic and social dimensions of sustainability, were not specifically considered in our study. However, Garrido et al. (2017) assessed stakeholders' appreciation of the ecosystem services of dehesa in northern Extremadura (Spain), some of which are similar to some of the functions analysed in this study. As an added value of our study, some indicators have not been considered in other studies. Moreover, the scope of previous studies was limited to certain demands or functions of society towards/from the dehesa. Our study considers and integrates a wide range of aspects and criteria, such as the demands of society, functions of the dehesa, and CAs/CSs to be implemented to improve the sustainability of the dehesa. Consequently, this study provides a "solution- and action-oriented assessment", which is strongly recommended in sustainability assessment studies (Troullaki et al., 2021).

The results obtained show that Andalusian society clearly values the importance of the environmental dimension of the dehesa in generating well-being and contributing to a sustainable future for the region. This is followed by the economic and social dimensions of the dehesa. In contrast, Arriaza and Gómez-Limón (2011) found that Andalusian citizens prioritised the economic dimension, followed by the environmental dimension, when valuing the multifunctionality of agriculture. However, these authors analysed the agricultural sector as a whole and did not focus on the particularities of the dehesa.

In terms of economic demands on the dehesa, our results show that society assigns a high priority to the typical, safe, healthy and quality agricultural products provided by the dehesa, as well as to its contribution to leisure, recreation, rural tourism and eco-tourism. Along these lines, the most important economic function, according to the demands of society and the knowledge of experts, is the production of forest products, such as acorns, cork and wood. These products and services should be the basis for elaborating market strategies (local, regional, national) within the management and rural development plans of the dehesa. Garrido et al. (2017) showed that provisioning services (products obtained from ecosystems) from dehesa landscapes were the most valued among stakeholders at the local level in northern Extremadura, Spain. They also revealed that recreation and eco-tourism services are highly valued. Similarly, in four focus group discussions reported by Gaspar et al. (2016), the authors also placed the main function of the dehesa as a provider of products; however, they especially valued high-quality food products of animal origin. Furthermore, Escribano et al. (2018)

consulted 30 experts to assess the sustainability of the dehesa and ranked the profitability of the farm and the percentage of the animal diet based on grazing as the most important economic indicators.

Regarding the environmental demands on the dehesa, our results indicate that society values the production of a typical and quality landscape, as well as other multiple environmental benefits of different nature linked to the ecosystem services and externalities generated by the dehesa (e.g. conservation and maintenance of species, fire prevention, climate and air improvement, CO₂ absorption, erosion reduction, regulation of water cycles and aquifer recharge). These are the most requested demands among all society's demands, not only environmental ones. The most prioritised environmental function, according to societal demands and expert knowledge, is biodiversity. Garrido et al. (2017) also highlighted that biodiversity conservation was the most appreciated service at regional level in northern Extremadura (Spain). Consequently, proper management of dehesa farms is necessary to conserve and enhance all the environmental benefits that generate utility for society, which, in addition, can have a multiplier effect on other economic activities in rural territories (e.g. tourism). On the other hand, as society increasingly perceives and demands these environmental benefits, new policy instruments are needed to enhance their provision.

In terms of society's social demands on the dehesa, its role as historical and cultural heritage and the high value of its educational, cultural and scientific functions stand out. In fact, the social functions received a high priority based on expert knowledge and society's demands, especially those related to the preservation of tangible and intangible cultural heritage.

At a global level, society clearly perceives the dehesa as a productive and economic system associated with highly differentiated cultural patterns (e.g. crafts linked to local resources, traditions and festivals linked to agricultural and forestry practices, transhumance and various livestock practices). Garrido et al. (2017) also showed that people highly appreciate the economic and cultural services provided by the dehesa. Along these lines, in a survey conducted in municipalities around a National Park in Extremadura, respondents valued the socio-economic functions of the dehesa more than the environmental ones (Moral et al. 2014).

Our results also show that CA related to tree renewal and CSs related to tree management, such as formation pruning and health pruning, are of high priority for the sustainability of the dehesa. CA supporting soil and water conservation is also of particular relevance. Similarly, WWF/Adena (2014), Costa Pérez et al. (2006), Moral et al. (2014) and Olea

and San Miguel-Ayanz (2006) also focused their recommendations for improving the management of dehesa farms on actions related to tree management and renewal. The first two authors, together with Escribano et al. (2014) and Gaspar et al. (2008), also recommended reducing the intensity of exploitation, not analysed here, while Martínez-Agirre and Astrain (2020) recommended low planting density. WWF/Adena (2014) also highlighted the importance of soil protection, similar to the highest priority CA of soil and water conservation in our study. Similarly, Escribano et al. (2018) stated that stocking rate (number of animals per amount of land) and the degree of soil erosion or soil loss are the most important environmental indicators of dehesa. On the other hand, although high stocking rates have been associated with greater environmental degradation, Gaspar et al. (2007) also pointed out that higher stocking rates tend to make dehesa farms more profitable.

Considering the margin for improvement of the different CSs as well as their priority, our results show that gully correction and limestone amendments should be the focus of attention for future improvement actions in the dehesa. To our knowledge, these are specific CSs that have not been analysed elsewhere.

4.4 Policy implications

In terms of policy making, it is important to note that the conflict between economic and environmental policy measures is a complex issue that has been the subject of much debate and discussion. The three pillars of sustainability (economic, social and environmental) are often seen as competing with each other, and policy makers have to choose between prioritising one over the others. However, it is important to recognise that these three pillars are interdependent and cannot generally be considered in isolation from each other. In this context, the ANP methodology can help to define more precise policy measures by taking into account multiple criteria within the three pillars of sustainability, as well as the interdependencies between them, as outlined in section 4.2 "Methodology and data". This may be an interesting line of future research.

Therefore, policy decisions often seek a balance between the three dimensions of sustainability. This is because all three are important for creating a sustainable future. The environmental dimension is important to preserve natural resources and ecosystems, the economic dimension is important to create a prosperous economy, and the social dimension is

important to ensure a good quality of life for all citizens. The a priori reasons for not implementing specific measures in favour of only one dimension are to ensure that all three dimensions are addressed and to avoid unintended consequences. For example, a measure focusing only on the environmental dimension could have unintended consequences on the economic and social dimensions. Similarly, a measure that only focuses on the economic dimension could have unintended consequences on the environmental and social dimensions. However, discriminatory measures may in some cases be justified to favour any dimension(s) of sustainability in policy design or planning if they are necessary to achieve a legitimate objective (as in the sensitivity analysis carried out). This could include protecting the environment, reducing inequality or promoting economic growth.

The results obtained in this study suggest that policies related to the conservation of soil and water, the renewal of trees, and, most critically, the correction of gullies by masonry and limestone amendments, should have a high priority to improve the sustainability of dehesa in Andalusia. In general, it is possible for CAs/CSs in different dimensions of sustainability to be compatible and complementary, provided that they are carefully planned and implemented in a way that takes into account possible trade-offs and synergies between them. For example, measures to conserve soil and water can also have positive effects on biodiversity and the preservation of cultural heritage, and vice versa. However, it is also true that, in some cases, policy measures aimed at improving one dimension of sustainability (such as the economic dimension) may have negative impacts on another dimension (such as the environmental dimension). In such cases, it may be necessary to find ways to mitigate or balance these negative impacts in order to achieve a more sustainable outcome. While such CAs/CSs are technically feasible, the actual implementation of policies that favour their implementation depends on the availability of resources and the support of relevant stakeholders. In this regard, there is strong institutional support for the dehesa in Andalusia through the Master Plan for Andalusian Dehesas [Plan Director de las Dehesas de Andalucía], approved by Decree 172/2017 of 24 October 2017 (CAPDER, 2017). The general objectives of the plan are: 1) To improve the economic viability of farms and the productive sectors and activities associated with the Andalusian dehesas; 2) To promote territorial cohesion, improving the quality of life in the territories, supporting the diversification of the rural economy, and enhancing the cultural and ethnographic attributes of the Andalusian dehesas; and 3) To conserve the ecosystem in the territories where the dehesas are located.

It is also important to highlight that the results obtained in this study can be used to design public policies to improve the sustainability of dehesa ecosystems in other regions/countries. In order to transfer these results to other dehesa regions, it would be necessary to carry out a similar study in those regions using the same methodology and assessing the environmental, economic and social demands of the society in those regions. The results of the study could then be compared with the results of the original study in Andalusia, to determine similarities and differences in the prioritisation of environmental, economic and social factors and possible conservation actions and sub-actions that could improve the sustainability of the dehesa in those regions. This information could serve as a basis for the design of specific public policies and conservation strategies for these new regions. Furthermore, the methodology used in this research can serve as a reference to assess the sustainability associated with other management actions in other agro-ecological systems and/or other regions. This is because the methodology, based on AHP and MCDA, is a systematic and structured approach to evaluate and prioritise different conservation actions or sub-actions (CAs/CSs) according to their expected contribution to improving sustainability. This methodology can be applied in other agro-ecological contexts and systems by adapting the specific criteria and priorities to the specific needs and demands of the local society and ecosystem. In addition, the use of surveys and expert knowledge can provide valuable information on stakeholder priorities and concerns, and help identify the most effective actions to improve sustainability in these other contexts.

5 Conclusions

The objective of this study was to contribute to the design of public policies for the sustainable management of the dehesa ecosystem in Andalusia, southern Spain, by prioritising a wide range of conservation actions and sub-actions. To this end, the study developed an AHP model. The model was evaluated on the basis of a survey of society in the dehesa areas of Andalusia and the knowledge of dehesa experts. The AHP model made it possible to integrate the demands of society into the process of designing policies towards sustainability, understood as being associated with the general well-being of society. The AHP is a fully compensatory method aligned with weak sustainability, allowing trade-offs between environmental, economic and social objectives. The methodological process presented can serve as a guide for assessing

the sustainability associated with management actions in other agricultural systems and/or regions.

The results show that society gives high priority to the environmental dimension of the dehesa ecosystem. The highest priorities among society's demands are the production of typical and high-quality landscapes and the conservation of biodiversity. However, among the functions of the dehesa, the social functions contribute most to sustainability, in particular the preservation of cultural heritage. After the social functions, forest production (economic function) and biodiversity (environmental function) are the highest priority functions. The highest priority CAs to improve the sustainability of the dehesa are soil and water conservation and tree renewal. The most critical CSs are the correction of gullies by masonry and limestone amendments.

The results obtained highlight the importance of the non-productive functions of the dehesa and their consideration together with its productive role for the design of public policies aimed at stimulating sustainable development processes from an economic, social and environmental point of view. Furthermore, the results can contribute to the design of public policies towards greater sustainability of the dehesa not only in Andalusia, but also serve as a reference for other studies on the dehesa in other regions.

Future research and applications of the presented methodological framework can focus on further refining and improving the model, e.g. by using ANP, which allows interdependencies between criteria to be taken into account. In addition, future research can explore the potential of integrating the AHP methodology with other methodologies, such as life cycle assessment, to provide a more comprehensive sustainability assessment. Furthermore, the sustainability approach used in this research can be complemented with other approaches, such as ecosystem services and complex social-ecological systems, to inform sustainable development strategies and policies.

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